

THE REGULATION OF JUVENILE DETENTION IN JORDANIAN LEGISLATION AND INTERNATIONAL TREATIES

ADEL AHMAD ALHARFOUSHI

Faculty of Law, Al-Ahliyya Amman University, Amman, Jordan. Email: harfoushi.a@gmail.com

Abstract

This study explores the legal framework governing the detention of juvenile offenders under Jordanian legislation, with a particular focus on the Juvenile Law No. (32) of 2014. The research aims to assess the extent to which Jordanian provisions align with international standards related to juvenile justice, especially those enshrined in the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) and the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (The Beijing Rules). The study adopts a descriptive-analytical methodology and is structured into two main chapters. It addresses the concept of juvenile delinquency, the categorization of juvenile age groups, the scope of criminal responsibility, and the legal measures and sanctions applicable at various stages. It further examines the legal basis, conditions, and justifications for juvenile detention under both Jordanian law and relevant international instruments. The research identifies legislative gaps, particularly the procedural regulation of juvenile detention, the absence of express provisions regarding the exceptional nature of such measures, and the limited recognition of the specialized role of public prosecutors in juvenile cases. In conclusion, the study provides a set of recommendations aimed at enhancing legislative clarity and ensuring compliance with international legal standards to better protect the best interests of the child and promote a rehabilitative approach to juvenile justice.

Keywords: Juvenile Delinquency, Jordanian Juvenile Law, Procedural Provisions, Juvenile Police.

1. INTRODUCTION

In light of the growing number of crimes committed by this demographic, the phenomenon of juvenile delinquency stands out as one of the most significant social, educational, and legal challenges face modern societies. This reality necessitates a specialized legal approach that balances the best interests of the juvenile on one hand, and the imperatives of justice and societal protection on the other. In today's world, children under the age of eighteen are considered among the most critical age groups, with estimates from the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs placing their number at approximately 2.4 billion, which represents nearly one-third of the world's population. Accordingly, the protection of children's rights and the assurance of their treatment in accordance with international legal standards are among the primary objectives pursued by both national and international legal systems.

There is a variance among countries in defining childhood, or what is legally termed the juvenile stage. They consider the social and economic respective as well as the customary contexts. The majority of legal systems have adopted the standard definition of childhood as the period during which a person has not yet reached the age of eighteen. This definition plays a pivotal role in determining the age of criminal responsibility for juveniles by establishing the minimum and maximum limits of juvenile status.

This determination is grounded in various legal, social, and cognitive criteria. It also includes the mental capacity of juveniles in order to comprehend their actions. However, criminal responsibility alone is not regarded as a fixed standard for legal and judicial treatment of juvenile offenders, as is the case with adults. Rather, the juvenile's circumstances and psychological and social conditions are taken into account at all stages of investigation and trial.

Accordingly, the Jordanian legislator has established specific rules governing the detention of juvenile offenders. These rules set forth conditions for their detention based on clear legal justifications. They also require that this exceptional measure can be implemented only under a judicial order and with full consideration for the best interests of the juvenile.

In addition, the position adopted by the Jordanian legislator concerning the criminal rules on juvenile detention is largely aligned with a number of international conventions and instruments such as the ***Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989)***. This Convention obligates the State Parties to safeguard the rights of the child and establishes criminal procedures that differ from those applicable to adult offenders. These provisions encompass several general principles for dealing with juveniles, including, but not limited to: the presumption of innocence, the prohibition of pretrial detention except under limited and exceptional circumstances, and the guarantee of a legal and judicial environment conducive to the fair adjudication of juvenile cases.

Accordingly, it may be said that the Jordanian legislator has made efforts to align domestic law with international conventions and instruments concerning juvenile rights. However, in practice, numerous challenges continue to hinder the effective implementation of legal safeguards, particularly those related to juvenile detention.

These challenges also affect the broader application of procedural guarantees during the investigation and trial phases. Therefore, establishing a legislative framework that ensures the incorporation of procedural guarantees for juveniles is essential. In addition, promoting rehabilitative and reintegrative measures aimed at their social reintegration constitutes a crucial step toward achieving justice and protecting the rights of juvenile offenders.

1.1. Research Problem

The core issue addressed by this study lies in the fact that the legal procedures governing juvenile detention are inherently serious, as they directly affect the juveniles' personal liberty. This reality underscores the need to regulate such procedures in a manner that ensures the protection of juveniles' rights and freedoms during the preliminary investigation stage, particularly those relating to detention.

A legislative gap is evident in the legal framework governing juvenile offenders generally, under the *Jordanian Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014*, and more specifically in the provisions concerning detention, as the implementation of most procedures relies predominantly on the general provisions set forth in the *Code of Criminal Procedure*.

1.2. Research Questions

1. What is the nature of the procedural provisions governing the detention of juvenile offenders under Jordanian legislation and international instruments?
2. What are the legal safeguards related to the detention of juvenile offenders as established under Jordanian legislation and international instruments?
3. To what extent are the provisions regulating the detention of juvenile offenders in Jordanian law consistent with those stipulated in international instruments?

1.3. Objectives of the Study

This study aims to provide a critical and analytical examination of the legislative texts governing the detention of juvenile offenders under Jordanian law. It seeks to clarify the nature and legal character of such provisions and to assess their effectiveness in safeguarding the rights of juveniles throughout all phases of the criminal process, beginning with the initial inquiry, through preliminary investigation and trial, to the execution of judgments and associated detention-related decisions.

Additionally, the study endeavors to evaluate the consistency of Jordanian legislative provisions concerning the treatment of juveniles in criminal matters with international instruments. It aims to identify points of convergence and divergence in the procedures, conditions, and legal guarantees established for the detention of juvenile offenders.

1.4. Significance of the Study

The importance of this study lies in its treatment of a legal topic of growing interest at both national and international levels. It addresses a relatively under-researched area of law by focusing on the legal provisions governing juvenile detention under Jordanian legislation and examining the extent to which these provisions comply with relevant international conventions and standards. The researcher aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the Jordanian legislator's position regarding the legal safeguards afforded to juvenile offenders, while also reviewing relevant judicial precedents.

Moreover, the study incorporates scholarly insights drawn from the experiences of jurists, legal researchers, and law students. It also presents an in-depth review of national laws and international instruments concerned with the protection of juveniles' rights and freedoms.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The subject of juvenile justice has received growing attention in legal scholarship, with various studies exploring different dimensions of juvenile delinquency and procedural safeguards within national and comparative contexts. These studies, while diverse in scope and methodology, have collectively contributed to a more nuanced understanding of the legal protection afforded to juveniles during criminal proceedings.

However, a closer examination reveals a recurring focus on general trial guarantees and procedural rights, whereas the specific issue of **juvenile detention**, particularly in the **pretrial stages**, remains underexplored. This study seeks to address that gap by critically analyzing the legal provisions governing the **detention of juvenile offenders** under Jordanian legislation and their alignment with international standards.

One of the most recent contributions to the field is the study by **Saif (2024)**, titled "*Safeguards in Juvenile Interrogation during the Preliminary and Final Investigation Phases under the Jordanian Juvenile Law*". This study focuses on the procedural guarantees available to juveniles during the investigation phases, distinguishing between the preliminary inquiry and the final investigation before the Juvenile Court. Saif's work is significant in clarifying the legal foundation of these phases and the protective mechanisms embedded in **Jordanian Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014**. By adopting a descriptive-analytical methodology, the study systematically explores the statutory safeguards, including the right to legal counsel and protections against arbitrary measures. While it offers valuable insights into the investigative process, its scope is limited to investigatory guarantees and does not engage with the broader procedural and substantive complexities surrounding juvenile detention. In contrast, the present study extends the inquiry into the **nature, scope, and legality of detention procedures**, thereby complementing and deepening the analytical discourse initiated by Saif.

Similarly, the doctoral thesis by **Khawaldeh (2021)**, titled "*Criminal Safeguards for Juvenile Trials in Jordanian and Comparative Law*", provides a comprehensive examination of the guarantees available to juveniles during trial proceedings. The study is divided into three parts: the first addresses the criminological underpinnings of juvenile delinquency; the second evaluates the role of competent judicial and administrative authorities; and the third focuses on the conduct of law enforcement agencies in juvenile cases. Khawaldeh adopts both a comparative and analytical framework, drawing on Jordanian, Egyptian, and French legal systems. This comparative approach is particularly useful in highlighting normative divergences and best practices. However, the thesis tends to emphasize trial-stage protections and judicial conduct, with less attention to **pretrial detention** and its procedural thresholds. In this respect, the present study provides a novel contribution by focusing specifically on **the legality and procedural safeguards of juvenile detention during the earlier stages of criminal prosecution**, especially within the context of the Jordanian legal framework.

Further expanding the regional scope, **Al-Sharaqah (2021)** presents an analytical study entitled "*Safeguards in Juvenile Interrogation during the Pretrial Phase in Palestinian Legislation*". This work investigates legal guarantees afforded to juveniles during evidence gathering and preliminary investigation under **Palestinian Juvenile Law No. 4 of 2016**, with reference to **Jordanian Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014**.

The study analyzes procedural safeguards applied by both the juvenile police and prosecution, and examines legal mediation mechanisms. The comparative methodology employed is effective in revealing both legislative convergence and divergence in juvenile protection.

Nonetheless, the focus remains confined to **investigatory procedures** and **non-custodial interventions**, without undertaking a comprehensive analysis of the **institutional framework, legal justifications, and due process considerations surrounding juvenile detention**. In contrast, the present study explicitly investigates these procedural and institutional aspects, while also assessing compliance with international standards such as the **Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989)**.

Taken together, these previous studies underscore the growing scholarly concern with juvenile justice and the procedural treatment of minors in conflict with the law. They demonstrate a strong emphasis on investigation and trial guarantees, with a noticeable gap concerning **the specific legal regime of juvenile detention** particularly the judicial, legal, and administrative conditions under which such detention is ordered and executed. This study addresses that lacuna by offering a focused analysis of **detention as a distinct legal measure**, examining its substantive and procedural regulation under Jordanian law, and evaluating its conformity with international human rights instruments. It also considers the broader implications for **juvenile criminal responsibility**, the **role of judicial discretion**, and the **institutional mandates** governing the deprivation of liberty.

In sum, while previous scholarship has laid a strong foundation in mapping the general terrain of juvenile rights and procedural safeguards, this study advances the discourse by offering a specialized examination of **juvenile detention**, a measure that carries significant legal and moral implications for the rights, dignity, and rehabilitation of minors. It situates this issue within both the **national legislative context** and the **international legal framework**, thereby contributing to the ongoing efforts to enhance juvenile justice systems in line with global human rights norms.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a dual-method approach to examine the legal provisions governing the detention of juvenile offenders under Jordanian legislation. First, the **descriptive method** is employed to review and present the relevant legal texts that regulate juvenile detention, primarily focusing on **Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014** and the **Jordanian Code of Criminal Procedure**. This method facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the national legislative framework and also extends to the examination of international legal instruments, including the **1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child** and the **United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (Beijing Rules)**. The goal is to identify points of convergence and divergence between domestic law and internationally recognized standards. Complementing this is the **analytical method**, which is used to interpret and evaluate the effectiveness of the national and international legal texts in protecting the rights of juveniles. This includes an assessment of judicial practices and practical implementation, alongside an analysis of relevant legal scholarship. Through this method, the study seeks to produce objective findings that contribute to the development of a coherent legal framework aligned with international juvenile justice principles and respectful of the rights of the child.

The scope of the study is defined along three dimensions. **Applicably**, it is confined to the legal provisions governing the detention of juvenile offenders, particularly within the framework of Jordanian law and relevant international instruments. It focuses specifically on the **Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014**, the **Jordanian Code of Criminal Procedure**, the **Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989)**, and the **Beijing Rules**. **Geographically**, the study is situated within the legal and institutional context of the **Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan**, where the relevant national laws are applied. **Temporally**, the research covers legislative and judicial developments up to the end of **2024**, with particular emphasis on the most recent amendments and legal trends to ensure that the study remains current and reflective of evolving legal standards.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. The Conceptual Framework of Juvenile Detention in Jordanian Legislation and International Instruments

The concept of the "juvenile" or "juvenile offender" varies depending on the legal and social criteria used in its definition. In legal contexts, the juvenile is typically defined according to age-based standards. The Jordanian legislator adopts a fixed chronological criterion, whereby any person who has not reached the age of eighteen is considered a juvenile. This definition aligns with the approach taken by many international legal systems and instruments. Conversely, the sociological perspective views the juvenile through a behavioral lens, applying a more flexible standard that considers the individual's physical, mental, and psychological maturity. This perspective highlights the multifaceted nature of childhood and adolescence, acknowledging that maturity is not determined solely by age.

Within the same context, the definition of the "juvenile offender" raises particular legal and social considerations. A juvenile offender is generally understood as a minor who, at a certain age, exhibits deviant behaviors or inclinations that may lead to the commission of criminal acts or socially unacceptable conduct. The **Jordanian legal system** addresses the detention of juvenile offenders through a set of legislative provisions, most notably those found in **Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014**, as amended, in addition to the relevant provisions of the **Jordanian Code of Criminal Procedure No. 9 of 1961**, as amended.

4.1.1. The Concept and Nature of Juvenile Delinquency in Jordanian Legislation and International Instruments.

Linguistic and legal terminology often intersect, with legal and jurisprudential terms grounded in linguistic meaning that serves as the foundation for their technical usage¹. This interplay is evident in the term "*juvenile*", which linguistically refers to something recently occurring, and has evolved to denote a child of young age, prior to physical or mental maturity. The term "*delinquent*" means to deviate or to stray from the path, thus connoting behavioral deviation or moral transgression. In Jordanian legal doctrine, juvenile delinquency refers to actions committed by minors that fall within the scope of criminal behavior or antisocial conduct.

These actions are treated with a distinct legal and procedural framework that reflects both the need to uphold public order and the imperative of protecting the juvenile's rights and prospects for rehabilitation. The Jordanian legislature has thus developed a specialized body of rules—both substantive and procedural—aimed at regulating the legal status of juveniles in conflict with the law. These rules are shaped not only by domestic legal priorities but also by the obligations arising from international treaties, including the **Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989)** and the **United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (Beijing Rules)**.

These international instruments emphasize that the treatment of juvenile offenders must be fundamentally different from that of adults, guided by the principles of protection, rehabilitation, and reintegration, rather than punishment and retribution. They encourage state parties to adopt procedural safeguards and alternative measures that avoid the deprivation of liberty, except as a last resort and for the shortest appropriate period.

In this light, the concept of juvenile delinquency under Jordanian law is situated within a dual framework national and international that seeks to balance the interests of justice, societal protection, and the rights and best interests of the child. This study proceeds from this conceptual foundation to examine how detention, as one of the most severe legal measures that may be applied to a juvenile, is regulated and justified within this framework.

4.1.2. The Personal and Substantive Scope of the Concept of the Juvenile Offender

Many Arab and foreign countries have sought, through their juvenile justice legislation, to align with international standards and instruments related to juvenile justice. This has often been achieved through the enactment of specialized laws addressing all matters concerning juvenile offenders, at-risk youth, and children in need of care or rehabilitation. The primary objective behind enacting dedicated juvenile laws is to ensure the legal and social protection of children's rights and freedoms, while also emphasizing a preventive and rehabilitative approach. This comprehensive approach includes mechanisms for prevention, social care, correction, and rehabilitation, with the ultimate aim of positively reintegrating juveniles into society and reducing the likelihood of behavioral relapse, which can significantly impact both the individual's future and public safety at large.

The **Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC)** defines a child in **Article 1** as "every human being below the age of eighteen years unless, under the law applicable to the child, majority is attained earlier." This definition establishes eighteen as the upper age limit for applying the Convention's provisions, while allowing signatory states to determine the age of legal majority in accordance with their national circumstances. The Convention thus accommodates diverse legal systems by recognizing that criminal responsibility may begin earlier under what is termed "partial" or "diminished" responsibility. The **United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (Beijing Rules²)** further support this flexibility.

These rules define a juvenile as "a child or young person who, under the legal system concerned, may be dealt with for an offense in a manner different from an adult.

" Similarly, the **UN Guidelines for the Prevention of Juvenile Delinquency** describe a juvenile as "any person under the age of eighteen³." These definitions demonstrate a consistent pattern across international instruments: while providing a general framework, they leave the precise determination of age thresholds to the discretion of national legislators, taking into account each country's legal, social, political, and cultural context.

Regionally, the upper age limit for juveniles also varies. The **Egyptian Constitution**, in **Article 80** (amended 2019), defines a juvenile as anyone under the age of eighteen. Similarly, **Sudanese Law**, under **Article 4 of the Juvenile Law of 2010**, adopts eighteen as the upper age limit. In contrast, the **Qatari Juvenile Law No. 1 of 1994**, as amended, defines a juvenile more narrowly as a person aged seven or older but under sixteen at the time of the offense or when found in a state of vulnerability to delinquency. Moreover, in the **French law**, the age of juvenile status is also set at eighteen, though exceptional cases allow for criminal responsibility from as young as thirteen⁴. In the **United States**, the age of juvenile jurisdiction varies by state, generally ranging between sixteen and eighteen years.

Against this backdrop, it can be concluded that most Arab and international legal systems broadly align with the international standard of setting eighteen as the upper limit for juvenile status⁵. In **Jordan**, the legislator adopts a similar approach under **Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014**⁶, defining a juvenile as any person under the age of eighteen. The law categorizes juveniles into three distinct age groups for legal purposes:

- *Child*: under twelve years of age,
- *Adolescent*: from twelve to under fifteen years,
- *Youth*: from fifteen to under eighteen years.

Additionally, **the Law on the Supervision of Juvenile Behavior No. 37 of 2006**⁷ defines a juvenile as "any person who has reached the age of seven but has not yet reached the age of eighteen, whether male or female." Remarkably, this definition lowers the minimum age of juvenile classification compared to the 2014 Juvenile Law, which sets the lower threshold at twelve. This discrepancy likely reflects the legislator's intent to extend **social protection and preventive intervention** to children from the age of seven, thereby enabling early support and shielding them from potential exposure to delinquency or social risk.

4.1.3. The Concept of Juvenile Delinquency in Jordanian Legislation and International Instruments

Juvenile delinquency generally refers to the emergence of behaviors that deviate from socially accepted norms. The most serious manifestation of such deviance occurs when a juvenile commits an act that constitutes a punishable offense under the law—this is what may be termed *criminal deviation*, or more specifically, *juvenile delinquency*⁸.

From a sociological perspective, juvenile delinquency may also encompass minor infractions committed by children and adolescents that breach legal norms or violate the prevailing social order, even if not classified strictly as crimes⁹.

The **United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (Beijing Rules)**, in **Rule 2.2 (Scope and Definitions)**, define a juvenile as a child or young person who may be held accountable for an offense in a manner different from that of an adult under the applicable legal system. The same rule defines criminal behavior as any conduct—whether by act or omission—that is subject to penalty under relevant legal provisions. Accordingly, a *juvenile offender* is described as a child or young person who is alleged to have committed or has been found guilty of an offense.

The acts committed by juveniles that are criminalized under the law form the **substantive scope** of juvenile delinquency in its narrow legal sense. This concept focuses solely on minors who engage in unlawful conduct with criminal intent, for which the legislator prescribes a penalty or a preventive measure. While legal definitions of juvenile delinquency tend to focus on the age range during which criminal responsibility is either mitigated or waived, **psychological and sociological approaches** regard juvenile delinquency as a developmental phase characterized by particular traits and challenges¹⁰.

Notably, in 1995, sociologist **Charles Tittle** developed the **Control Balance Theory** to explain deviant behavior deemed undesirable by society. The theory posits that behavior is shaped by the ratio of control a person is subjected to versus the control they are able to exert. A balanced control ratio leads to conformity, whereas imbalance, whether surplus or deficit, may lead to deviant behavior such as theft or exploitation. This imbalance is seen as the result of complex interactions among motivation, restraint, and opportunity, ultimately leading to behavioral disorder. Therefore, when examined from a **social perspective**, the definition of a "delinquent juvenile", based on behavioral criteria appears overly broad and imprecise. It lacks clear distinctions between positive and negative forms of deviation and fails to provide a definitive measure of social harm. In contrast, the **legal definition** is more specific, focusing on unlawful conduct and the resulting harm, thereby offering a more structured basis for legal intervention.

Most international conventions¹¹ and national legal systems recognize that the concept of **juvenile delinquency** encompasses not only juveniles who are in direct conflict with the law but also those **at risk of delinquency**. An "at-risk juvenile" refers to a minor exhibiting signs of social vulnerability, suggesting a potential for future engagement in criminal behavior¹². Such recognition broadens the legal and policy response beyond punitive measures to include preventive and protective interventions. In fact, it is noteworthy that the **Jordanian Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014** does not explicitly define the term "at-risk juvenile." Instead, **Article 33** outlines circumstances in which a child is considered vulnerable to danger, delinquency, or in need of care and protection. This legislative approach allows for flexible interpretation while identifying specific situations that necessitate legal and social intervention.

Commendably, the Jordanian legislator distinguished between **juvenile offenders** and **at-risk juveniles**, thereby enabling appropriate protection measures tailored to the child's specific condition. This differentiation aligns with the **principle of preventive care**, emphasizing the best interests of the child as a foundational element in social policy.

As a member of the family unit, widely considered the cornerstone of society, the juvenile is particularly susceptible to familial and social pressures that may predispose them to deviant behavior. In such instances, the intervention of competent authorities is essential to implement preventive strategies and safeguard the juvenile from pathways leading to delinquency.

4.2. Section Two: Juvenile Criminal Responsibility

The issue of juvenile criminal responsibility is one of the most complex and debated topics in both legal theory and practice. It has attracted sustained attention from jurists and legal scholars throughout history, and has undergone significant evolution over time—both within the framework of international legal instruments and in comparative legal systems. These developments reflect an ongoing effort to refine the conceptual foundations and practical applications of juvenile criminal responsibility in a way that balances accountability, protection, and rehabilitation.

4.2.1. The Scope of Juvenile Criminal Responsibility in Jordanian Legislation and International Instruments

In its most general sense, ***criminal responsibility*** refers to the legal capacity of an individual to bear penal consequences, either in the form of punishment or preventive measures, for acts that constitute criminal offenses under the law¹³. Although legal definitions of criminal responsibility may vary, they consistently emphasize a person's ***cognitive and volitional capacity*** that is, the ability to comprehend the nature of their actions and the intent to commit the act in question.

This principle is affirmed in ***judicial precedent***, notably in **Jordanian Court of Cassation Decision No. 1696/2019**, issued on **27 October 2019**. Upon analysis, this ruling reflects the core legal doctrine underpinning criminal responsibility in Jordanian law, in line with previous jurisprudence. The Court held that the defendant, suffering from paranoid schizophrenia at the time of the offense, lacked the necessary cognitive capacity to be held criminally accountable. Consequently, the Court deemed the defendant a public safety risk and ordered therapeutic confinement in the **National Center for Mental Health** until recovery could be medically verified. This case underscores the judicial system's obligation to balance the ***protection of individual rights*** particularly of mentally ill defendants and with the ***collective interest in public safety and justice***.

In terms of juvenile offenders, both international legal standards and domestic legislation emphasize a ***graduated approach*** to determining criminal responsibility. This approach considers the juvenile's ***mental, emotional, and biological development***, ensuring that legal accountability corresponds with their evolving capacities and maturity. Significantly, most international instruments ***do not mandate a uniform minimum age*** of criminal responsibility binding on all signatory states.

Instead, the ***Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC)***¹⁴ encourages states to set a minimum age below which children are presumed ***incapable of violating criminal law***, without specifying a fixed number.

Similarly, the **Beijing Rules**¹⁵ stress that this minimum age should not be set “too low,” urging consideration of emotional, mental, and intellectual maturity in determining whether a juvenile can be held criminally liable.

The absence of a universal standard has resulted in *variations among national legal systems*. However, many jurisdictions adopt **seven years of age** as the lower threshold for criminal responsibility, reflecting a common compromise between the need for protection and the recognition of agency in younger children.

Jordanian legislation reflects this flexible yet cautious approach. While **Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014** addresses the legal framework for juvenile proceedings, it also embeds the principle that *criminal responsibility must be proportionate to the juvenile’s capacity for discernment and understanding*. The law thus promotes a child-sensitive justice system that integrates legal safeguards with rehabilitative goals, consistent with international obligations¹⁶.

One of the most significant substantive amendments introduced by the Jordanian legislature under **Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014** was the *raising of the minimum age of criminal responsibility from seven years*¹⁷, as previously stipulated in earlier legislation, to *twelve years*¹⁸. This shift reflects Jordan’s alignment with international legal standards and evolving normative trends that call for enhanced legal protection for children, especially in response to the increasing complexities and risks of modern life that disproportionately affect juveniles.

To this end, the current Juvenile Law classifies the juvenile age span into **three developmental stages**:

- **Child**: below twelve years of age.
- **Adolescent**: from twelve to under fifteen years.
- **Youth**: from fifteen to under eighteen years.

Based on this categorization, the *stages of criminal responsibility* under Jordanian legislation are outlined as follows:

1. Stage of Absolute Non-Responsibility

This stage encompasses the period from birth until the juvenile reaches twelve years of age. During this time, the child is *presumed to lack legal discernment* and therefore cannot bear criminal responsibility, regardless of the nature of the act committed¹⁹. Importantly, this legal exemption applies *only to the juvenile perpetrator*; it does *not extend to accomplices* or co-conspirators in the offense, whose responsibility remains intact. Additionally, this lack of responsibility does *not negate the criminal nature of the act itself*, which retains its legal classification as a punishable offense. The exemption affects only the personal liability of the child.

2. Stage of Diminished or Partial Responsibility

This stage applies to juveniles who have attained the age of **twelve** but have not yet reached **eighteen**, encompassing both the adolescent and youth categories.

Here, the juvenile **exceeds the age of legal discernment**, thereby incurring criminal responsibility in principle, but is still not considered to possess full legal capacity. The law accordingly applies **attenuated or modified sanctions**, tailored to the offender's age, developmental status, and rehabilitative potential.

Articles **25 and 26** of the Jordanian Juvenile Law outline a **graduated system of penalties** for offenses committed by adolescents and youths, distinguishing between **felonies, misdemeanors, and infractions**, and prescribing measures that emphasize **correction over punishment**. This reflects a deliberate **policy of progressive accountability**, whereby the law moves from total exemption to mitigated responsibility in recognition of the juvenile's evolving capacity.

3. Stage of Full Criminal Responsibility

Full responsibility is deemed to commence once the juvenile reaches the age of **eighteen**. At this point, the individual is considered a legally **competent adult**, capable of full awareness and understanding of their actions. As such, they are subject to **the full scope of the Penal Code, the Code of Criminal Procedure, and other applicable laws**, without recourse to the special protections provided under the Juvenile Law. Regarding the **determination of the juvenile's legal age**, Article **6(a)** of the Juvenile Law provides that **official civil registry records (birth certificates or national ID data)** shall serve as **conclusive evidence** of age, unless proven to be fraudulent. In instances where no such records exist or the juvenile is **unregistered or lacks documentation**, Article **6(c)** stipulates that the court shall **refer the individual to a medical committee** formed under the applicable regulations for the purpose of **age estimation**. Notably, **the time required for medical assessment is counted as part of the trial period**²⁰, ensuring procedural fairness and efficiency. Through these provisions, the Jordanian legislature demonstrates a **nuanced approach to juvenile criminal responsibility**, harmonizing its domestic framework with international norms while ensuring procedural safeguards that are both child-sensitive and grounded in legal certainty. In line with its international obligations, the Jordanian legislator has sought to harmonize national juvenile justice provisions with global standards, most notably those set forth in the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) of 1989. Article 40(3)(a) of the CRC urges State Parties to establish **laws, procedures, authorities, and institutions specifically applicable to children** alleged or accused of having infringed the penal law. In particular, it calls for:

- The determination of a *minimum age* below which children shall be presumed incapable of violating the criminal law; and
- The promotion of *non-judicial measures* where appropriate, such as diversion programs, provided that such measures uphold the child's legal rights and guarantees in full.

Further, Article 40(4) of the CRC emphasizes the importance of *alternative arrangements* tailored to the well-being of the child and proportional to both the circumstances of the offense and the child's individual situation. These may include care orders, guidance and supervision, probation, foster care, education and vocational training programs, among other *alternatives to institutional care*.

Reflecting these principles, the *Jordanian Juvenile Law* (Articles 24–26) establishes a set of *non-custodial measures* and *reduced penalties* tailored to the juvenile's age group. These measures are defined as any court-ordered *sanction that does not involve deprivation of liberty*, and are applied at the discretion of the juvenile court depending on the circumstances of the offense and the offender²¹.

Under Article 24, the juvenile court may impose the following non-custodial measures on adolescent or youth offenders:

- Reprimand or admonition;
- Release to the custody of a parent or guardian;
- Mandatory community service;
- Enrollment in vocational training programs;
- Imposition of specific duties or prohibitions;
- Participation in rehabilitative programs;
- Judicial supervision.

When imposing such measures, the court must also consider the provisions of Articles 25 and 26, which allow for *replacement of penal sanctions* with non-custodial measures in cases of *felonies or misdemeanors* committed by adolescents, and in *misdemeanor or infraction cases* committed by youths, where *mitigating circumstances* are present²². However, the law does *not provide for mitigation in felony cases involving youth offenders*, a legislative omission that has prompted courts to *resort to the general provisions* of the *Penal Code* in such instances. This was evident in *Court of Cassation (Criminal) Decision No. 2856/2018*, issued on 25 November 2018, where the court mitigated the sentence based on the defendants' confession and the waiver of personal claims. Upon analysis, this judgment reveals a critical legislative gap: the *absence of clear legal grounds for mitigation in felony cases involving youth offenders*, which creates ambiguity and compels reliance on general adult criminal provisions—contrary to the specialized nature of juvenile justice. This underscores the need for *legislative reform* to include *explicit mitigating grounds for youth offenders* in serious criminal cases, to avoid inconsistencies and ensure alignment with the rehabilitative goals of juvenile justice. Moreover, the law gives the court *broad discretion* to impose *any of the listed non-custodial measures* regardless of whether the offender is an adolescent or a youth. This flexibility contrasts with the more detailed provisions regarding *custodial measures*, such as placement in juvenile rehabilitation centers, which are *specifically assigned to age groups and differentiated by the severity of the offense*.

Comparatively, Egyptian law under *Juvenile Law No. 31 of 1974 (as amended)* prohibits imposing any *penal sanctions* on children under fifteen years of age. Instead, Article 7 lists non-custodial measures similar to those found in Jordanian law: reprimand, release to guardianship, vocational training, imposition of duties, judicial probation, placement in social care institutions, and in some cases, admission to specialized medical facilities. This reflects a more structured and categorical approach to age-based differentiation in juvenile sanctions, emphasizing *protective and rehabilitative mechanisms* over punitive responses.

4.3. Legal Organization of Juvenile Detention in Jordanian Legislation and International Instruments

The legal foundation for detaining juveniles under *Jordanian Juvenile Law No. (32) of 2014* is derived from multiple legislative provisions that aim to regulate this exceptional measure and guarantee the rights of the juvenile²³, taking into consideration the distinctive features of the juvenile stage and its long-term implications on both the individual and society²⁴. **Article (8)** of the aforementioned law regulates the detention of juveniles in circumstances where the needs of the investigation so require²⁵. The ***authority to order detention is exclusively vested in the competent judicial authorities*** and must be exercised in accordance with clearly defined legal conditions. The law explicitly **prohibits administrative detention** of juveniles, regardless of the nature or seriousness of the surrounding circumstances. This prohibition is emphasized in the introductory phrase of **Article (8)**: “**Notwithstanding any provision in any other legislation...**”, which underscores the ***priority and supremacy of this provision*** in matters concerning juvenile detention over any conflicting legal text.

While the Jordanian legislator ***did not expressly state*** that detention is to be employed ***as a measure of last resort and for the shortest appropriate period***, as is required under **international human rights instruments**, the restriction of detention powers solely to the judiciary implies an ***underlying legislative intent consistent with international standards***²⁶, particularly those outlined in **Article 37(b) of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC)**. This reflects a commitment to uphold legal safeguards and to prohibit detention except in ***exceptional and necessary circumstances*** justified by the interests of the investigation and, at times, the best interest of the juvenile. The legislator’s commitment to ensuring juvenile protection is further illustrated by the ***clear divergence between the legal rules governing the detention of juveniles and those applicable to adults***. For example, **Article 9(d)** of the *Juvenile Law* stipulates that the detention of a juvenile accused of a misdemeanor or felony may not exceed **ten days** and must occur within a ***juvenile rehabilitation center***. This contrasts sharply with **Article (114)** of the *Jordanian Code of Criminal Procedure*, which permits:

- **Seven days** of initial detention in misdemeanor cases punishable by up to two years’ imprisonment,
- and up to **fifteen days** in felony cases.

Thus, the **legal characterization** of juvenile detention reflects its nature as a **precautionary, exceptional, and temporary investigative measure**. Despite its impact on personal liberty, juvenile detention **does not amount to a criminal penalty**, as it is imposed during **pre-trial or trial phases** and not as part of a final judicial judgment that would justify the imposition of a punitive sanction.

4.3.1. Conditions and Justifications for Juvenile Detention

The Jordanian legislator acted commendably by stipulating the necessity of appointing a specialized Public Prosecution to handle juvenile cases, which constitutes a legal safeguard that contributes to protecting the best interests of the juvenile and expediting their rehabilitation and reintegration into society. However, the legislator's use of the term "designation" (*takhṣīṣ*) as found in Article (7) of the Juvenile Law is imprecise. The requirement of designation does not necessarily imply that the assigned public prosecutors possess the necessary specialization. In this context, the competence of the Public Prosecution extends beyond the mere legal classification of the offense committed by the juvenile; it also entails possessing the requisite experience and ability to understand the juvenile's personality, family, and social circumstances, as well as the underlying causes that led them to commit the unlawful act. Therefore, it would have been more appropriate for the Jordanian legislator to employ the term "specialized" instead of "designated," so that the phrase would read: "appointing a specialized Public Prosecution to handle juvenile cases." This would ensure that specialization is a mandatory requirement for those entrusted with such responsibilities. One of the criticisms directed at the wording of Article (7) is that the legislator entrusted the Judicial Council with the task of designating members of the Public Prosecution to hear juvenile cases, yet failed to consider offenses committed by juveniles that fall under the jurisdiction of the State Security Court, which is administratively subordinate to the Military Judiciary Directorate and lies outside the authority of the Judicial Council. Consequently, such designation and specialization would not extend to Public Prosecutors assigned to juvenile cases within the jurisdiction of the State Security Court. This situation renders such procedures incompatible with international treaties and conventions, particularly those that require cases to be adjudicated by a specialized, independent, and impartial judicial authority²⁷.

1. Legal Conditions for Detention Under Jordanian Law and International Instruments

The **Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948)** adopted by the **United Nations General Assembly**, sets out core rights to be universally protected. In particular, **Article (9)** states: "**No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention or exile.**"

Given the grave nature of detention, which infringes on individual liberty and undermines the **presumption of innocence**. This measure is encircled by **strict legal safeguards** appropriate to its severity.

The **Jordanian Code of Criminal Procedure** governs general rules related to all investigative measures, including detention, covering **its justification, duration, and permissible grounds**.

However, in cases involving juveniles, **special provisions of Juvenile Law No. (32) of 2014** apply in accordance with the established legal principle that “**lex specialis derogat legi generali**” (special law overrides general law).

Among the most important legal **conditions** governing the detention of juvenile offenders under both statutes are:

- **Article (4/b) of the *Juvenile Law*** provides: “**Notwithstanding any other legislation, a person under the age of twelve shall not be held criminally liable.**” Therefore, **detention is not permitted for juveniles under twelve years of age**, as they lack criminal capacity. The **detention orders must be issued by a competent judicial authority**, such as the **Juvenile Prosecutor or Juvenile Judge**, and not by the police or administrative bodies. This requirement constitutes a **core procedural safeguard** in juvenile proceedings.
- On the other side, a **substantive condition** for juvenile detention is that the juvenile must be charged with a **felony or a misdemeanor punishable by imprisonment**. Thus, detention is permitted only in the following cases:
 - ✓ **Felony offenses;**
 - ✓ **Misdemeanors punishable by more than two years’ imprisonment;**
 - ✓ **Misdemeanors punishable by two years or less**, but only when they involve **theft, intentional or negligent bodily harm resulting from traffic accidents**, or when the juvenile lacks a **known and stable residence within Jordan**.

Therefore, **detention is not permitted** for misdemeanors punishable **solely by fines or administrative violations**. In addition, while the legislator has divided juveniles into two main categories, “**adolescents**” (12–15 years old) and “**youths**” (15–18 years old), this distinction has **not been reflected** in the rules governing detention orders. This **inconsistency** does not align with the legislator’s intent to ensure **graduated protections based on age**. In the researcher’s view, the law **ought to have clearly linked detention powers to these age-based categories**, ensuring enhanced protections for younger juveniles in line with their developmental stage and best interests²⁸.

2. Legal Justifications for Detention in Jordanian and International Law Article (114) of the *Jordanian Code of Criminal Procedure* outlines several legal grounds for detention that apply to both adults and juvenile²⁹, including:

- **Preservation of evidence and witness integrity** during the investigation phase, such as:
 - ✓ Preventing **tampering with evidence**.
 - ✓ Avoiding **intimidation or coercion of witnesses**.
 - ✓ Preventing **communication with accomplices or instigators**.

- **Maintaining public order**, particularly in cases where the alleged crime poses a threat to **national security or public safety**³⁰.
- **Protection of the juvenile suspect**, including:
 - ✓ Preventing reoffending,
 - ✓ Safeguarding the juvenile from **potential retaliation or harm** from others involved in the offense.

Accordingly, the **legal rationale for juvenile detention** seeks to balance **the interests of justice** with **the protection of the juvenile's rights**. Detention decisions must be made with **careful legal justification**, in accordance with **constitutional norms and statutory protections**. Then, the question triggers the mind is that should these legal justifications cease to exist or no longer apply? Actually, the judicial authority is **obligated to release the juvenile**. Failure to do so would render the detention **unlawful** and subject to **nullification**. Moreover, under **Article (124)**³¹ of the **Code of Criminal Procedure**, **detention orders may be appealed**, reinforcing procedural guarantees.

Therefore, a detention must be based on **sufficient evidence** indicating that the juvenile³²:

- Has **likely committed the offense**, or
- **Poses a danger** to himself or others, or
- **May flee from justice**.

This ensures that detention is used only **when necessary to secure the juvenile's appearance before the court**.

A comparison between **Article (114)** of the Code of Criminal Procedure and **Article (9)** of the Juvenile Law reveals that the **Juvenile Law imposes more restrictive rules** on detention:

- The maximum initial period of detention is **ten days**;
- It may be renewed **once only**, for another **ten days**;
- In contrast, the **Code of Criminal Procedure allows detention**:
 - ✓ For up to **one year** for felonies punishable by temporary detention,
 - ✓ And up to **eighteen months** for other felonies.

Furthermore, the **Public Prosecutor or Court** may release a detained juvenile **on bail or personal guarantee**, regardless of whether the charge is a misdemeanor or a felony, provided this secures the juvenile's presence during investigation and trial.

Article (9) of the Juvenile Law also stipulates that **the Public Prosecutor may only renew detention once**, after which the case must be referred to the court for any further extension, which must **not exceed ten additional days**. This structure reflects **the legislator's concern for the psychological and humanitarian well-being** of juveniles.

However, there remains a **legislative shortcoming**: the **lack of an exhaustive enumeration of the legal justifications and conditions for detention within the Juvenile Law itself**, which opens the door to the application of general criminal procedure rules designed for adults. For the sake of fully protecting juvenile rights and fulfilling the **principle of the child's best interests**, all matters related to detention should be **addressed exclusively within the Juvenile Law**, without reliance on procedures applicable to adult suspects.

CONCLUSION

This study has endeavored to shed light on the legal provisions governing the *detention of juvenile offenders* under *Jordanian legislation*, particularly as set forth in the *Juvenile Law No. (32) of 2014*, with the objective of assessing the extent to which these provisions align with the *international standards of juvenile justice*. This study has addressed the conceptual framework of juvenile delinquency by examining the definition of a "juvenile in conflict with the law", and the scope of *criminal responsibility* attributed to juveniles. It also explored the *measures and penalties* prescribed both under Jordanian law and in *relevant international instruments*, most notably the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) and the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (The Beijing Rules). In addition, the study analyzed the legal basis for the detention of juveniles, along with its *conditions and justifications*, while also reviewing the *practical procedures* adopted in this context by the competent authorities. The research employed a descriptive and analytical methodology and was structured into two main chapters and an introduction. It concluded with a number of key findings and recommendations that may contribute to the enhancement and reform of the legal framework governing juvenile detention, in a manner that upholds the principles of justice and ensures the protection of the best interests of the child. These findings and recommendations are summarized as follows:

First: Findings of the Study

1. Through the examination of **national legislation, comparative regional legal systems**, and **international instruments** addressing the issue of juvenile detention, it is evident that, despite differences in defining the minimum age of **criminal responsibility and legal capacity**, there is general consensus on the necessity of establishing a **dedicated legislative framework** that comprehensively regulates all legal provisions concerning juveniles. This stems from the delicate nature of dealing with this age group and the significant implications it holds for their future.
2. It is observed that the **Jordanian legislator**, in the **Juvenile Law No. (32) of 2014**, referred several procedural aspects concerning juveniles, particularly those related to the powers of **law enforcement authorities**, including the **initial and preliminary investigation stages** to the provisions of the **Code of Criminal Procedure**, without explicitly regulating them within the Juvenile Law itself. This stands in contrast to the treatment of **juvenile trial procedures**, which were thoroughly addressed by the legislator in all of their stages.

3. The **Juvenile Law** classifies juveniles into three distinct age categories—**child**, **adolescent**, and **youth**—for the purpose of determining criminal responsibility. However, the legislator directly allocated certain **measures** to the adolescent and youth categories without leaving discretionary power to the judiciary in this regard. Furthermore, while **mitigating factors** were explicitly provided for **adolescents** in cases of **felonies** and **misdemeanors**, the law fails to specify similar mitigating grounds for **youth** in cases involving **felonies**, thereby creating a **legislative gap** that necessitates legal reform.
4. The **Juvenile Law** does not explicitly require the **specialization of public prosecutors** in juvenile cases. Rather, it merely stipulates the designation of a number of **public prosecutors** to handle such cases, without establishing a formal specialization mechanism.
5. The Jordanian legislator does not explicitly state in **Juvenile Law No. (32) of 2014** that **detention** constitutes an **exceptional measure**, to be used only for a **limited period** and as a **last resort**, as emphasized in **international instruments and standards**. Nevertheless, this principle may be inferred from the cumulative reading of various provisions within the law.

Second: Recommendations of the Study

1. It is recommended that the Jordanian legislator explicitly incorporate within the Juvenile Law the procedural provisions governing the detention of juveniles, including its conditions and justifications, particularly during the preliminary investigation stage, rather than referring to the Penal Code and the Code of Criminal Procedure. Codifying these procedural rules directly within the Juvenile Law would enhance legal clarity, strengthen the protection of juvenile rights, and support the fair administration of justice.
2. It is recommended that the Jordanian legislator expand the scope of precautionary measures stipulated in the Juvenile Law, and introduce additional non-custodial measures not currently provided for, such as supervised liberty and victim compensation. It is also recommended to specify the competent authority responsible for imposing and executing such measures, while allowing for their modification—whether by reduction or intensification—depending on the juvenile’s conduct during the period of enforcement. This would ensure procedural flexibility and serve the best interests of the juvenile.
3. It is recommended to amend Article 25 of Juvenile Law No. (32) of 2014 to include a specific provision permitting the application of discretionary mitigating circumstances in cases where a youth (al-fatah) commits a felony. This amendment would establish legislative balance and align with Article 26(c) of the same law, which permits the application of discretionary mitigation in the case of felonies committed by an adolescent (al-murahiqa).

4. It is recommended that the Jordanian legislator amend Article 7 of the Juvenile Law to explicitly require specialization among members of the Public Prosecution in juvenile matters, in alignment with Article 3 of the same law, which mandates the establishment of a specialized police department, and Article 15(b), which requires expertise for juvenile judges and judges responsible for enforcing sentences. Mandating such prosecutorial specialization would contribute to enhancing the quality of judicial procedures and strengthen the protection of juvenile rights in accordance with international standards.
5. It is recommended that the legislator introduce an explicit provision in the Juvenile Law stipulating that detention is an exceptional measure of limited duration, to be used only as a last resort, as affirmed by relevant international conventions and rules on juvenile justice.

Footnotes

- 1) These include, for example: The United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (the Beijing Rules), the Riyadh Guidelines, the United Nations Rules for the Protection of Juveniles Deprived of their Liberty, the Convention on the Rights of the Child, and other international instruments.
- 2) The United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (The Beijing Rules), General Principles, Part One, Rule 2.2.
- 3) UNICEF, *Guidelines on the Procedural Rights of Child Victims and Witnesses of Crime*, 1st ed., published by the Egyptian Ministry of Justice, 2019, p. 72.
- 4) On January 21, 2021, the French Senate unanimously approved a law setting the legal age of sexual consent with minors at 13 years. This effectively lowers the "age of sexual majority" by two years from the previously established age of 15. At this age, a child in France is legally able to engage in consensual sexual relations without legal repercussions. However, the child is still legally prohibited from entering into a marriage contract until reaching the legal age of majority, which is set at 18. <https://web.archive.org/web/20201122140324/http://www.senat.fr/lng/en/index.html> 20/5/2025.
- 5) At the state level, 33 U.S. states have not set a minimum age of criminal responsibility. For federal crimes, however, the minimum age of criminal responsibility is 11 years. The highest age for criminal responsibility is found in Massachusetts, where it is set at 18 years with no exceptions. In contrast, the lowest age of criminal responsibility is in North Carolina, where it is set at just 6 years. (Source: U.S. Congress – Senate Bill 4327, 118th Congress, accessed May 20, 2025)
- 6) **Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014**, published on page 6371 of Official Gazette Issue No. 5310 dated 02/11/2014.
- 7) This law regulates the monitoring of the behavior of juveniles between the ages of seven and eighteen, by prohibiting them from engaging in activities that may negatively affect their growth and development—such as purchasing or using narcotic drugs and alcoholic beverages, begging, or entering nightclubs and bars. It also outlines the penalties for violations and strengthens legal oversight of places that may expose minors to such activities.
- 8) Ibrahim, Akram Nashat. (1991). *Juvenile Delinquency: Its Causes and Preventive and Therapeutic Care to Address It*. Naif Arab University for Security Sciences, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, p. 30.
- 9) Al-Amoush, Ahmad Falah. (2006). *Family Structure and Juvenile Delinquency in Emirati Society*. Mu'tah Journal for Human and Social Sciences, Vol. 21, pp. 203–230.

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- 11) Beijing Rules, General Principles, Article 3.1: In expanding the scope of the rules, it is stated that "The relevant provisions of the Rules are not only applicable to juvenile offenders but also to juveniles who may be subject to proceedings for acts that would not be punishable if committed by an adult."
- 12) Abd Al-Sattar, Fawzia. (1998). *Criminal Treatment of Children: A Comparative Study*. Dar Al-Nahda Al-Arabiya, Cairo, p. 77.
- 13) **Najm, Mohammad Sobhi.** (2023). *The Concise Guide to the Code of Criminal Procedure*. Dar Al-Thaqafa, Amman, p. 262.
- 14) Article 40(3)(a) of the 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child.
- 15) Beijing Rules, General Principles, Part One, Rule 4.1.
- 16) **Article One of the Iraqi Juvenile Law No. 6 of 1972 (as amended in 1980), Article Three of the Lebanese Law for the Protection of Juveniles in Conflict with the Law or at-Risk No. 422/2002**
- 17) **Article (2) of the Juvenile Reform Law No. 16 of 1954 and the Juvenile Law of 1968 and its amendments.**
- 18) **Article 4(b) of the Jordanian Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014** states: "Notwithstanding any other legislation, no criminal proceedings shall be brought against anyone who has not completed twelve years of age."
- 19) Article (2) of the Jordanian Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014 defines: 1. *Adolescent*: A person who has completed twelve but not yet fifteen years of age. 2. *Youth*: A person who has completed fifteen but not yet eighteen years of age.
- 20) See **Article (6) of the Jordanian Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014.**
- 21) See **Article (6) of the Jordanian Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014.**
- 22) See **Article 25, paragraph (e), and Article 26, paragraphs (d) and (e) of the Jordanian Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014.**
- 23) **Sorour, Ahmed Fathi.** (2016). *Al-Wasit fi Qanun al-Ijra'at al-Jaza'iyyah* (The Intermediate Text in the Code of Criminal Procedure), 10th ed., Dar Al-Nahda Al-Arabiya, Cairo, p. 777.
- 24) **Hosni, Mahmoud Naguib.** (1973). *Criminology*, 2nd ed., Dar Al-Nahda Al-Arabiya, Cairo, p. 700.
- 25) **Namour, Mohammad Saeed.** (2021). *Fundamentals of Criminal Procedure: A Commentary on the Code of Criminal Procedure*, 2nd ed., Dar Al-Thaqafa, Amman, p. 402.
- 26) This principle is confirmed by Article (9) of the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on 16 December 1966, as well as Article (5) of the *European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms*.
- 27) See **Article 40(2)(3) of the 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child**, which outlines the fundamental guarantees for children accused of infringing the penal law, including the right to be presumed innocent, to be informed promptly of the charges, to have legal assistance, and to have the matter determined without delay by a competent authority.
- 28) **Article (63) of the French Code of Criminal Procedure** states: "No person may be detained except by order of a judicial police officer, based on a request or order from the Public Prosecutor." **Article (47) of the Lebanese Code of Criminal Procedure** states: "A suspect may not be detained except by a decision of the Public Prosecution, and for no more than forty-eight hours." **Article (40) of the Egyptian**

Code of Criminal Procedure No. 150 of 1950, as amended, provides: "No one may be arrested or detained except by order of the legally competent authorities."

- 29) **Al-Joukhadar, Hassan.** (1992). *Law of Juvenile Delinquents*, 1st ed., Amman, p. 53.
- 30) **Najm, Mohammad Sobhi.** (2023). *The Concise Guide to the Code of Criminal Procedure*, Dar Al-Thaqafa, Amman, p. 179.
- 31) **Article (124)** of the *Code of Criminal Procedure* states: "The decision issued by the Public Prosecutor or the Magistrate Judge to detain the accused, extend the detention, release him, or leave him free... may be appealed."
- 32) This was affirmed by the Jordanian legislator in **Articles (111), (114), and (131)** of the **Code of Criminal Procedure No. 9 of 1961 and its amendments**, which outline the legal procedures and safeguards related to arrest, detention, and the rights of the accused.

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